

MODELING OF DISCRETE RADIAL REINFORCEMENT IN CURVED POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: The problem of how through-thickness reinforcement opposes the opening of delamination cracks in curved laminar structures is examined theoretically. Finite element calculations have been performed to show how the through-thickness reinforcement modifies the energy release rate of a delamination crack. Solutions are found for perfectly bonded and debonded cases. Energy conservation arguments are then used to define constitutive laws for equivalent continuous bridging springs acting on the delamination fracture surfaces. This step allows the immediate application of useful concepts from the literature on bridged cracks. Results are summarized for convenient use and trends are highlighted by relating the exact numerical results to analytical approximations for the perfectly bonded and debonded cases.

KEYWORDS: polymer matrix composite, stitch, laminate, delamination, finite element, bridging traction, bridged crack.

INTRODUCTION

In previous publications [1,2] simple approaches for predicting the amount of through thickness reinforcement required to suppress delamination in polymer matrix composites have been presented. A curved configuration originally defined by Kedward et al [3] and used for conventional curved composite laminates was adopted for the theoretical development of these prediction methods. Further evaluation of the adequacy of these simple methods is now accomplished through finite element analyses.

From a practical viewpoint a relatively small percentage of through thickness reinforcement has been proven to be effective in suppressing the propagation of delamination in impact damaged panels and at stepped transitions associated with local changes in laminate thicknesses. Similarly, it is anticipated, but as yet unproved experimentally, that delamination tendencies in curved structures subjected to bending loads, that tend to increase with the radius of curvature, can be suppressed by stitching.

One major incentive for the present work is the substantiation of the simple methods advanced by Cox et. al [1] enabling estimation of the minimum percentage of stitch reinforcement in the radial direction of curved laminates, necessary to suppress delamination in curved laminates subjected to static or fatigue loading. These simple methods can then be adopted by structural designers in their efforts to select prudent stitch densities and evaluate

the relative merits of a range of stitch formulations, i.e. fiber type and number of filaments per tow. The designer can then avoid the penalty of in-plane property degradation that can be created by fiber damage and distortion with excessive percentage of through thickness (stitch) reinforcement. In addition the closed form relationship developed can facilitate estimation of the type, area fraction and distribution of stitches that would represent effective percentages for various skin thickness and/or curvatures.

Other constraints are imposed by the textile machinery available and used by the fabricators of fiber preforms and the subsequent polymer matrix composites. Hence the contribution of the analysis tools developed and validated herein, which serve the designers in the vital interactions with the manufacturing activities. Typically the processes involved in the fabrication of stitched composites consist of some form of resin infiltration technique such as Resin Film Infusion (RFI) or Resin Transfer Molding (RTM).

The following development addresses the categories of well bonded and debonded interfaces between the stitch tow and surrounding matrix. This is shown to represent strong differences in performance and effectiveness of the through thickness reinforcement and therefore the selection can be influenced by both the reinforcing fiber and its surface characteristics.

THE DELAMINATION AS A BRIDGED CRACK

Consider the uniformly curved laminate depicted in Fig. 1, subject to opening bending moments, i.e. moments of such a sense that the through-thickness stresses developed, σ_r are tensile. The laminate has total thickness $2h$ and the radius of curvature of its mid-plane is denoted r_m . When the curvature is modest ($h/r_m < 0.2$), σ_r takes its maximum value in the uncracked laminate near the mid-plane. It will be assumed in the following that all delaminations occur exactly on the mid-plane. This will be reasonable for studying delaminations caused solely by the through-thickness stress acting on naturally occurring flaws.

Fig. 1: A delamination crack in a curved structure under opening bending moments, with bridging stitches indicated schematically

Attention is also restricted here to delamination cracks that initiate and propagate far from the ends of the curved structure or any holes. With this condition, Mode II sliding displacements are expected to be negligible. The problem can therefore be treated by examining purely Mode I opening.

When a delamination crack begins to propagate, it will be bridged by the stitches, as depicted in Fig. 1. The axial stresses in the stitches will be transferred to the laminate, tending to close down the delamination crack and reducing the crack tip stress intensity factor, K_{tip} . This closure effect can be represented by a system of bridging tractions acting on the fracture surfaces. The bridging traction will usually increase as the delamination crack opening increases, at least until the stitches fail. This enables the possible existence of a steady state mode of delamination crack propagation, in which the critical value, σ_c , of σ_I required to cause propagation of the delamination crack reaches a constant value, σ_1 , independent of the delamination crack length.

To enable concepts from the literature on bridged cracks to be invoked, an analogue with continuous bridging traction is now sought to the discrete unit cell model shown in Fig. 2a. The continuous model will be formulated to be energetically equivalent to the discrete model.

The unit cell with continuous bridging traction, p , acting on the delamination fracture surfaces is sketched in Fig. 2b. The laminate and stitch have been replaced by a homogenous orthotropic medium. The models of Figs. 2a and 2b will be called the “discrete” and “continuous” models, respectively.

For the continuous model, the linear bridging traction law is given by

$$p = \beta u \tag{1}$$

where $2u$ is the total crack opening, β the bridging stiffness parameter.

Fig. 2: (a) Detail of the geometry assumed for modeling a stitched laminate.
 (b) Analogue of continuous bridging tractions acting on an homogenized laminate

The fracture properties of the continuous model have already been analyzed in Refs. 1,4 and 5. From these prior works, the steady-state cracking stress, σ_1 is given by

$$\sigma_1 = \sqrt{\beta \Gamma_c} \quad (2)$$

where Γ_c is the intrinsic Mode I fracture energy of the stitched laminate. A fair estimate of Γ_c is

$$\Gamma_c = (1-c_s) \Gamma_m \quad (3)$$

where c_s is the area fraction of stitches, Γ_m is the fracture toughness of the unstitched laminate. More generally, Γ_c refers to the delamination resistance arising from crack tip processes. Given Eq. (3) or some other estimate or measurement of Γ_c , σ_1 is fully determined by the bridging stiffness parameter, β .

ESTIMATION OF THE BRIDGING STIFFNESS PARAMETER β

Shear Lag Approximation

The problem of a cylindrical inclusion (here the through-thickness segment of the stitch) being pulled out of a semi-infinite half space (here one half of the laminate with the boundary being the crack plane) to which it is well bonded was analyzed by Budiansky, Hutchinson, and Evans (BHE) using shear lag methods [6]. While BHE assumed isotropy in the cylinder and the half-space, it will serve to equate Young's modulus for their inclusion to the axial modulus of the stitch, E_s , here; and the through-thickness and shear moduli of their half-space to the through-thickness and shear moduli of the laminate, E_z and G_{zx} here. Integrating the stress fields of BHE's Eq. (25) yields displacements at the fracture surface and thence an estimate, β_{BHE} , for β :

$$\beta_{\text{BHE}} = \frac{\rho c_s E_s}{r_s} \quad (4a)$$

where

$$\rho = \left[\frac{2G_{zx}}{E_z} \left(\frac{c_s}{1-c_s} + \frac{E_z}{E_s} \right) \frac{-4(1-c_s)^2}{2 \log c_s + (1-c_s)(3-c_s)} \right]^{1/2} \approx \eta c_s^{1/2} \quad (4b)$$

and r_s is the radius of the stitch, η is a dimensionless factor of order unity. The shear lag analysis of BHE yields axial stresses in the stitch which fall exponentially with distance from the fracture plane with a characteristic length r_s/ρ . Thus if

$$h < r_s / c_s^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_s = \frac{u_o}{h} = \frac{\sigma_o}{E_s} \quad (6)$$

where u_o is defined in Fig. 2a and σ_o is the average stress in the stitch on the crack plane. Assigning $u=u_o$ (in this approximation only) and recalling that $p=c_s\sigma_o$, the estimate, $\beta_{unif}^{(1)}$, of β follows as

$$\beta_{unif}^{(1)} = c_s E_s / h \quad (7)$$

This was the estimate used for β in Reference 1. As pointed out in [2], the load from the stitch will deform the laminate, creating a dimple at the transition zones. This increases the crack opening, which decreases β . With laminate deformation taken into account, an improved estimate, $\beta_{unif}^{(2)}$, of β is given by

$$\beta_{unif}^{(2)} = \frac{c_s E_s}{h} / [1 + \frac{(1-\nu)r_s E_s}{h G_{zx}}] \quad (8)$$

Results from Finite Element Model

Numerous calculations were performed by finite element methods in reference [2] for the discrete cell model (Figure 2a) for two material systems:

System 1: a quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminate stitched with carbon fibers;

System 2: the same laminate stitched by glass fibers;

Values of β deduced from the FEM results for well bonded stitches are presented in Fig. 3. The FEM results have been normalized by the estimate β_{BHE} derived from the BHE model. The abscissa shows the ratio h/r_s .

Figure 3a shows calculations for material system 1 for $c_s = 0.008$ (a relatively low volume fraction of stitches); and three values of the curvature measure r_m/h . Results for $r_m/h = 200$ will be very close to the limit obtained for vanishing curvature. The case $r_m/h = 5.7$ represents the maximum degree of curvature that this work will recommend in designing stitched laminates. For large h/r_s solutions for all r_m/h approach a constant value, not far from unity. For small h/r_s , β falls well below β_{BHE} . The cut-off occurs near the expected condition, Eq. (5), i.e., near $h/r_s = 11$ for material system 1. For $h/r_s > c_s^{1/2}$ (the regime where BHE is appropriate), there is some separation of curves for different r_m/h , but the dispersion is moderate for curvatures in typical structures ($5 < r_m/h < 10$).

For $h/r_s < 5$, the BHE derived approximation seriously overestimates β , which would lead to nonconservative designs. This is the regime of thin laminates, which can deform very easily by buckling without significant axial displacement of the stitches. The regime $h/r_s < 5$ must be avoided by designers.

Figure 3b shows results of the same form for fixed curvature, $r_m/h = 9$; up to three representative stitching area fractions, $c_s = 0.008$ (low), 0.02 (moderate), and 0.06 (relatively high); and for the same two material systems. All curves show similar trends, being almost constant for $h/r_s > 10$ and low for $h/r_s < 5$. For these material systems, β/β_{BHE} is not far from

unity for $h/r_s > 10$. As Fig. 3 summarizes, the estimate β_{BHE} is fairly accurate for highly anisotropic materials (polymer composites).

Figure 4 shows FEM results for the case of debonded stitches for the two material systems with $c_s = 0.008$ and $r_m/h = 5.7$. The bridging stiffness parameter, β , is now normalized against the estimate, $\beta_{\text{unif}}^{(1)}$, derived by assuming uniform axial strain in the stitch (Eq. (15)). All the curves lie significantly below the ordinate unity, indicating that $\beta_{\text{unif}}^{(1)}$ is a nonconservative estimate. The discrepancy is associated with the contribution of laminate deformation and its effect on stitch compliance which was ignored in the formulation for $\beta_{\text{unif}}^{(1)}$. The dashed curve shows $\beta_{\text{unif}}^{(2)}/\beta_{\text{unif}}^{(1)}$ where $\beta_{\text{unif}}^{(2)}$ is the estimate of Eq. (8), which includes an approximate estimate of laminate deformation. This curve reproduces the magnitudes and trends with h/r_s quite well. Just as for well bonded stitches, designing structures with $h/r_s < 5$ is not recommended, because β becomes very small (ineffective stitching).

Fig. 3: Numerical results for the bridging stiffness parameter, β normalized against the estimate derived from the BHE model vs. the ratio of the laminate half-thickness to the stitch radius. Well bonded stitches. (a) Three different curvatures; material system 1. (b) Different stitch area fractions for two material systems.

Fig. 4: Numerical results for the bridging stiffness parameter, β , for the continuous model normalized against the estimate derived by assuming uniform axial strain in the stitch vs. the ratio of the laminate half-thickness to the stitch radius. Debonded, frictionless stitches.

Bounds for β

The bonded and debonded, frictionless cases for which solutions have been computed by finite element methods provide upper and lower bounds for β . Let $\beta^{(\max)}$ denote the upper bound and $\beta^{(\min)}$ denote the lower bound. Any case of intermediate debonding or nonzero friction must lie between these bounds.

For the well bonded case,

$$\beta^{(\max)} \approx \chi(E_s/E_z)\beta_{\text{BHE}} \quad (9)$$

where χ is given by [2]

$$\chi(E_s/E_z) \approx 0.23 + \frac{1}{14}E_s/E_z - \frac{1}{450}(E_s/E_z)^2 \quad (10)$$

For the debonded case,

$$\beta^{(\min)} \approx \beta_{\text{unif}}^{(2)} \quad (11)$$

The upper and lower bounds for the steady-state cracking stress, $\sigma_1^{(\max)}$, and $\sigma_1^{(\min)}$, can be determined from the bounds for β and Γ_c by Eq. 2. Figure 5 shows representative values for the carbon-epoxy system as functions of the area fraction of stitches, c_s . The intrinsic fracture energy was assigned the value 1 kJm^{-2} .

MINIMUM AREA FRACTION OF STITCHES REQUIRED TO SUPPRESS DELAMINATION

In Ref. 1 it was proposed that a practical criterion for an adequate density of stitching was the requirement that delamination occur at a higher external load than that required for failure by some other mechanism. In most cases, the other mechanism will be failure on the compressive (outer) surface of the laminate, usually by kink band formation [1,7]. Let the critical in-plane compressive stress for kinking failure be denoted σ_c . The compressive stress on the outer surface, $\sigma^{(o)}$, is related to the maximum radial stress, $\sigma_r^{(a)}$ which arises near the mid-plane, by [1,4]

$$\sigma_r^{(a)} / \sigma^{(o)} = \frac{h}{2r_m} \xi[h/r_m, E_z/E_x] \quad (12)$$

where E_x is the in-plane Young's modulus of the laminate; and ξ is close to unity. A fitted approximation to ξ can be found in [1]. In the following, it will be assumed that $5 < r_m/h < 10$, so that $\sigma_r^{(a)}/\sigma_r^{(o)}$. For typical carbon-epoxy laminates, in-plane failure occurs by kinking on the compressive side when $\sigma^{(o)} = \sigma_c \approx 500\text{MPa}$. Thus for the assumed curvature range, one requires σ_1 in the range $25 < \sigma_1 < 50\text{ MPa}$. This range is marked in Figure 5. If the stitches remain well bonded, the area fraction of stitching c_s for stitches of common denier ($r_s \leq 0.5\text{ mm}$) required to achieve high enough σ_1 to suppress delamination never exceeds 4%. If the stitches are assumed to debond, the required area fractions are much higher and care would have to be taken to select a suitably fine stitch denier. A stitch of radius 0.125 mm would support the top of the range for σ_1 when $c_s = 0.06$. Nevertheless, this is the most conservative outlook for what is probably an extreme case. Stitching densities of a few percent with a stitch spacing of at least several mm are likely to represent common and practicable conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

The problem of a delamination crack bridged by discrete stitches in a curved structure has been mapped onto an analogue in which the crack is bridged by continuous crack face tractions. Solutions for well bonded and debonded, frictionless stitches form bounds to the general case. The bounds can be expressed as estimates of the critical stress for delamination, from which bounds for the volume fraction of the stitching required to suppress delamination can be deduced. For polymer composites, stitch area fractions below 5% will be enough to suppress delamination. Another important conclusion of this study is that the ratio of the laminate half-thickness to the stitch radius should not be allowed to fall below 5. Stitching is ineffective in suppressing crack opening and therefore in raising the delamination fracture energy for laminates that are thinner than this.

Carbon stitches in a
carbon-epoxy laminate

Fig. 5: Bounds for the design stress σ_1 . The shaded bands indicate values required for representative values of the relative curvature and the critical stress for failure

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